

Date: April 2025

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Characterization of *M tuberculosis*: Implications of Diversity and Versatility on Pathogenesis, Treatment and Drug Development

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Abstract:

Mycobacterium tuberculosis, the causative agent of tuberculosis, continues to pose a significant global health burden despite advances in diagnosis and treatment. This review examines the taxonomic classification, evolutionary history, and genetic diversity within the *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* complex (MTBC). Special attention is devoted to the distinctive architecture of the cell envelope, consisting of peptidoglycan, arabinogalactan, mycolic acids, and various free lipids, which contribute to the pathogen's pathogenesis, virulence, intracellular survival, persistence, and resistance to antibiotics. Furthermore, it discusses emerging insights into the metabolic pathways that support Mtb's adaptation to hostile host environments and highlights current and potential therapeutic strategies targeting the cell envelope. This review elucidates the interplay between MTB genes and biochemistry, emphasizes the need for integrated strategies in TB drug development, and advocates for continued research into targeting the cell envelope to overcome drug-sensitive and drug-resistant tuberculosis.

Keywords: Tuberculosis, Cell Wall, Peptidoglycan, Mycolic Acid, Arabinogalactan, lipid metabolism, antimicrobial resistance, tuberculosis therapy.

Introduction

Tuberculosis is the world's second most common cause of death from a single infection, following closely behind coronavirus disease (COVID-19). Shockingly, TB has claimed nearly double the number of lives compared to HIV/AIDS. In 2022, there were 1.3 million deaths, with 7.5 million newly diagnosed TB cases reported worldwide [1]. Despite advances in diagnosis and treatment over the last five decades, tuberculosis (TB) remains a global health concern, costing the lives of millions each year, straining healthcare systems, and presenting a problematic riddle for researchers. This "consumption," "lung phthisis," or "wasting away" disease is caused by the bacteria *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* [2]. This organism is highly resistant to many antibiotics due to its thick cell covering that

prevents the penetration of antibiotics. This thick cell covering acts as a barrier to the penetration of antibiotics; no wonder the Acid Fast Bacilli (AFB) test requires heating to ensure that the carbol-fuchsin dye penetrates the cell envelope [3].

A deeper understanding of the organism, including its ancestry and cellular functionality, is crucial to effectively combat antimicrobial resistance in tuberculosis. This review aims to characterize *M. tuberculosis*, which will serve as a foundation for a better understanding of the disease's dynamics and pathology and a springboard to further research in diagnosis and tackling antimicrobial resistance.

General Classification

Mycobacteria tuberculosis belongs to the order Corynebacteriales. Within this order is a clade (a group of organisms that includes a common ancestor and all the descendants) consisting of four genera (Corynebacteriaceae, Dietziaceae, Mycobacteriaceae, and Nocardioceae) distinguished by the possession of a type A1 γ meso-diaminopimelic containing peptidoglycan. The genus Mycobacteria was named "myco-bacteria" due to the possession of the longest carbon atom stretch of mycolic acids (C60-C90), in comparison with Corynebacteria (C22-38), Rhodococi (C30-54), Dietzia (C34-36), and Norcadia (46-64) [4].

The family *Mycobacteriaceae* consists of a single genus, Mycobacteria [5,6]. Members of this genus are aerobic, non-motile, non-spore-forming, non-capsulated, slightly curved, or straight rods with a size of 0.3-0.6 μ m. Colonies on culture media appear coloured, ranging from white to orange, smooth or rough, non-hyphenated, raised, and thick with a nodular or wrinkled surface [7-9]. Mycobacteria cells can endure low oxygen concentrations when allowed to settle slowly through self-generating oxygen. A rapid shift from aerobic to anaerobic conditions poses the risk of cell death. They grow at an optimal temperature of 37°C, pH of 6.4-7.0, 5-10% oxygen, and CO₂, with a 14-15h generation time under optimal conditions [10]. Members of this genus are deeply acid-fast, catalase-positive, and oxidase variants [11]. Except for one species, *M. leprae*, which cannot be cultivated in vitro, all other members of this group are versatile chemoheterotrophs capable of utilizing a range of substrates such as carbon, energy, and nitrogen sources [12,13]. Since all culturable mycobacteria species, except for *M. bovis*, can convert glycerol to pyruvate, mycobacteria culture media contain glycerol and asparagine as carbon and nitrogen sources [14]. Many mycobacteria species can grow on simple media like modified Sauton

agar. To aid the growth of cultured clinical strains, specialized egg-based media have been developed, including Middlebrook 7H10 and 7H11 agar, Löwenstein-Jensen agar (LJ agar), and Middlebrook 7H9 and 7H12 broth. While mycobacteria do not exhibit pigmentation on culture media (non-photochromogenic), adding dyes like malachite green enhances colony identification [15-17].

The members of the genus Mycobacteria can be categorized into four groups based on their clinical relevance. The first group includes species that cause tuberculosis, while the second group comprises those that cause leprosy (known as *M. leprae*). The third group includes non-tuberculous species, which consist of 140 species that cause various mycobacterial diseases in humans and animals. Finally, the fourth group comprises free-living mycobacterial species, including two species with 57 subspecies [6,18].

The Mycobacteria Tuberculosis Complex (MTBC)

Prior to the advent of molecular diagnostic techniques, all acid-fast-positive organisms causing tuberculosis were collectively identified as a single species - *M. tuberculosis*. Within this species, strains were distinguished based on factors such as the degree of virulence and biochemical and serological properties. In 1954, Ernest Runyon and his colleagues introduced a better classification system that relied on the period of colony formation. The genus was divided into two categories: slow-growing species, which form visible colonies after seven days of incubation, and rapid-growing species, which form colonies before the seventh day. [18]. Slow-growers possess virulence factors and are more resistant to decolonization during the AFB test, both in alkaline and acidic conditions. On the other hand, rapid-growers are mostly non-pathogenic and free-living. They show less resistance to acid-fast staining [19]. More

advanced techniques have discovered that members of this genera have considerable genetic homology observed when analyzing the standard 16S RNA genes [20]. A difference in the copy number of the ribosomal operons validates Ernest Runyon's classification. Unlike slow growers with only one copy of the ribosomal operon upstream of the 16S, 23S, and 5S rRNA genes, rapid growers have two copies of this operon upstream of the ribosomal RNA genes. This indicated that slow-growing species diverged from a common ancestor during their evolution, adapting to a pathogenic lifestyle [6,21].

The development of molecular typing techniques has improved accuracy in identifying strains and clades within mycobacteria. This has been particularly helpful in identifying tuberculosis-causing members adapted to infect humans and animals. These members are collectively known as the *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* Complex (MTBC) [22,23]. Phenotypic and phylogenomic data revealed eight closely related members of the MTBC responsible for causing tuberculosis-related diseases. They are 1) *M. tuberculosis* (humans), 2) *M. africanum* (humans), 3) *M. bovis* (humans and animals), 4) *M. bovis* BCG (non-pathogenic), 5) *M. caprae* (goats), 6) *M. pinnipedii* (seals), 7) *M. microti* (voles), and 8) *M. canettii* (humans) [24–28].

In 1994, Frederick Cohan proposed the theoretical concept of "ecotype," incorporating genetic and ecological criteria. An ecotype is defined as a group of genetically related individual organisms inhabiting a unique ecological niche, having been selected through evolution by purging non-beneficial genetic material found in common in related species and common ancestors [29]. Human-adapted members of the MTBC can be appropriately classified as ecotypes due to their minute but discernible and phenotypically significant

genetic divergence from other members of the genera, providing a survival advantage in their ecological niche. The geographical spread of MTBC lineages varies significantly, with some restricted to specific regions while others enjoy global distribution [30]. Human-adapted members of the MTBC share common characteristics. They have a genome size ranging from 4.38 to 4.42 Mb, identical 16S RNA, are obligate pathogens causing active pulmonary tuberculosis, transmit from host to host, lack a non-human host, and exhibit a distinct geographical distribution. Despite sharing over 99% genome homology, variations in host immunological response, pathology, and distribution have unveiled the existence of clades within the MTBC complex [6,21]. Contrary to the prevailing belief that human-adapted MTBC originated from *M. bovis*, recent research challenges this hypothesis. Phylogenetic studies indicate that the common ancestor of MTBC diverged into two significant species: *M. canettii* and the ancestor of the remaining MTBC, termed *M. prototuberculosis*. *M. canettii*, characterized by distinct features and an evolutionary trajectory influenced by Horizontal Gene Transfer (HGT), is predominantly found in the Horn of Africa, supporting the notion of an African origin for MTBC (Fig. 1). The spread of pathogenic MTBC strains is attributed to human migration. At the same time, climatic and host factors contribute to the development of various ecotypes [25,30].

Brites and Gagneux offer the latest classification of major phylogenetic lineages or ecotypes within the MTBC, with their names influenced by their suggested origin and geological prevalence. *M. tuberculosis* sensu stricto is in lineages 1-4, 7, and *M. africanum* in lineages 5 and 6 (their points of divergence influencing the numbering) [25]. Lineage 1, the East-African Indian (EAI) strain, is prevalent in India and Southeast Asia but originates in East Africa. Lineage 2, the East Asian or Beijing lineage, though globally

distributed, was first identified in Beijing. It exhibits high virulence and multi-drug resistance. Lineage 3, the Central Asian Strain (CAS), is found in Asia and parts of Africa, including CAS-Delhi in the Indian subcontinent and CAS1 Kilimanjaro in Africa. Lineage 4, Euro-American Lineage, has a worldwide distribution, possibly due to human migration and colonization from the Euro-American region. Lineage 5, West African 1, predominates in West Africa, particularly Nigeria, Ghana, and Benin, with a unique association with the Ewe ethnic group of Ghana. Lineage 6, West Africa 2, also predominates West Africa, exhibiting reduced virulence, and is commonly found among people living with HIV/AIDS. Lineage 7, the

Ethiopian strain, is exclusively found in Ethiopia, with ongoing research exploring a tropism linked to the genetic makeup of the Ethiopian population [25,31,32]. The MTBC classification also distinguishes between modern and ancient strains based on adaptability and virulence. Modern strains, exemplified by Beijing and EAI, demonstrate heightened virulence compared to their ancient counterparts. Specifically, modern strains 2, 3, and 4 exhibit greater virulence than ancient strains 1, 5, 6, and 7. The presence or absence partially informs this categorization of the genomic region known as TbD1. While this characteristic implies a close association between *M. africanum* and *M. bovis*, it does not conclusively establish homoplasia [33–35].

Fig 1: Phylogeny of 220 MTBC strains and their geographical distribution. Lineages are coloured triangles (a), while coloured dots (b) represent the dominant lineages in each region. Adapted from [29].

Genome and Evolution of MTBC

The study of genomics, proteomics, and nucleotide sequences augmented by computational analysis has significantly contributed to our knowledge of classification, characterization, epidemiology, and evolution of organisms. Different typing methods, such as spoligotyping and sequence typing, have enabled the identification of large sequence polymorphs (LSP), single nucleotide polymorphs (SNP), direct read sequences (DR), multilocus and repeating sequences, and restriction fragment length polymorphs (RFLP). These methods have helped to reveal differences within the MTBC ecotype that were previously unrecognizable [23,36,37].

In 1998, sequencing the MTBC model strain, *M. tuberculosis* H37Rv, revealed diversity, specificity, virulence, ecology, evolution, and physiology within this group. [36,38]. The genome sizes of different strains of tuberculosis were measured. The H37Rv strain had a genome size of 4 megabases (Mb), while the CDC1551 strain had a genome size of 4.4 Mb. The Beijing strain had a genome size of 4.8Mb, *M. africanum*, CAS, EAI5, and Haarlem strains all had a genome size of 4.4Mb, and the *M. bovis* and *M. microti* strains had genome sizes of 4.3Mb and 4.4Mb, respectively. The average nucleotide identity (ANI) among members ranged between 99.71% and 99.80% [21]. These research findings highlight the close genetic relationship between different members of the MTBC despite having different host specificities. Jia *et al.* identified 29 genes specific to strains adapted to humans and 15 genes specific to strains adapted to animals. They also noted the significant role of eight mammalian cell entry 3 (*mce3*) family genes in the pathogenesis of human infections. These genes encode Mce proteins, which are crucial for the entry and survival of bacteria within the human host and are absent in the animal

isolates. Furthermore, the researchers found that two enoyl-coenzyme A (CoA) hydratases (EchA1 and EchA18) were exclusively present in human isolates. These hydratases are essential in the fatty acid β -oxidation pathway. The absence of enoyl-CoA hydratase in animal-associated MTBC strains could impact fatty acid metabolism and cell wall synthesis [21].

The genome of members of the genus *Mycobacteria* consists of two large gene families, *pe* and *ppe*, with repetitive nature and high G+C content, constituting around 10% of the genome and accounting for 7-8% of the organism's coding potential (Fig. 2). The diversity of these genes has been used to classify *Mtb* into ecotypes [31,39]. The proteins coded by these genes, known for their roles in mycobacterial antigenic variation and host immune evasion, are specific to mycobacteria and often localized or secreted to the cell surface [40]. They are distinguished by conserved N-terminal domains comprising 100 and 180 amino acids, housing the proline-glutamic acid (Pe) and proline-proline-glutamic acid (PPE) motifs, from which they derive their names. The *M. tuberculosis* H37Rv strain has 100 *pe* genes and 69 *ppe* genes. These genes encode proteins that have polymorphic domains (PE-PGRS) and Major Polymorphic Tandem Repeats (PPE-MPTR) motifs, creating four protein subfamilies: PE, PE-PGRS, PPE, and PPE-MPTR (Fig. 2) [41]. The PP/PPE genes have a low copy number in rapidly growing non-pathogenic strains and a high copy number with varying potential for duplication and expansion among slow-growing pathogenic strains. The correlation between high copy number and pathogenesis suggests that these genes are crucial to the intracellular survival of pathogenic strains [33,41,42]. Further research into these families could unlock potential for tuberculosis prevention and treatment.

PE-PGRS: Tandem repeats of Asn GlyGlyAlaGlyGlcAla or its variant

PEP-MPTR: Multiple repeats of AsnXGlyXGlyAsnXGly

Fig 2: Depiction of the nucleotide length of the *pp/ppe* gene families. Antigenic and copy number variation result from translocation and duplication of the parts. Source [22] (Drawing made with Marvin sketch, 2019)

The MTBC evolves clonally, meaning there is little to no genetic recombination across strains. Fixity of the MTBC genome results in limited genetic diversity within the genus. This genetic "definitiveness" is controlled by evolutionary forces such as population bottleneck, selective sweep, compensation evolution, and reductive evolution [43]. Gagneux identified three levels of variation within MTBC: within the complex, across closely related clads, and clonal variation controlled by host-pathogen forces. To compensate for the possibility of genome decay, MTBC has a high gene copy number and recombination of insertion sequences. Horizontal gene transfer (HGT) also occurs to maintain genetic diversity within the MTBC. This happens due to high recombination potential, a high copy number, and host-pathogen forces [44]. According to Bentley *et al.* (2012), 51% of genes in the classic H37Rv strain result from duplication and domain shuffling events, and 3.4% comprise insertion sequences (IS). The gene with the most copies, IS6110, has up to 25 copies per genome in MTBC but only one or two copies in *M. bovis*. The recombination of IS6110 at various points on the genome accounts for this gene duplication, a significant cause of phenotypic variation [29,39,45].

Metabolic features of *M. tuberculosis*

M. tuberculosis enjoys metabolic plasticity. It possesses complete genes for major pathways with alternatives, shunts, and reverse pathways. The tubercle bacillus is thus metabolically flexible and can realign different metabolic pathways to enhance survival [46,47]. Its metabolic versatility may be attributed to the retention of its genome while transitioning from a free-living organism to one that lives in the most hostile environment in the human body- immune cells [48]. Unlike *M. leprae*, its close relative, *M. tuberculosis*, can produce the needed amino acids and cofactors from available carbon sources and use various carbon sources. Its genome is described as genetically redundant [6,14,49]. However, glycerol-cultured *M. tuberculosis* grows faster and reaches a higher density than those cultured with other carbon sources such as glucose and fatty acids. This accounts for the use of glycerol in preparing culture media for *M. tuberculosis* [15,50].

Carbon and Energy Sources

When fed with glucose, *M. tuberculosis* metabolizes glucose via the glycolytic-TCA

pathway. When fed with acetate or cholesterol, it uses the alternate pentose-phosphate pathway and the TCA cycle with unique oxidative and reductive branched pathways [46,51]. In a trehalose medium, the organism releases two enzymes, a trehalase and a trehalose phosphatase, to release two glucose molecules from trehalose. These enzymes are also activated during starvation, suggesting that during nutrient scarcity, *M. tuberculosis* utilizes trehalose incorporated in its cell envelope for survival [50].

In a glycerol-containing culture media, a series of enzymes break the glycerol to feed the glycolytic (Glyceraldehyde-3-PO₄) and gluconeogenesis (Fructose-1,6-bisphosphate) pathways, as shown in Fig. 3. During glycerol catabolism, *M. tuberculosis* uses an incomplete TCA due to its inability to synthesize sufficient α -ketoglutarate

dehydrogenase. It employs two shunts. One is the glyoxylate shunt, which reduces isocitrate to succinic acid. The other shunt oxidizes isocitrate to α -ketoglutarate, which is then presented to a special enzyme not found in the regular TCA, α -ketoglutarate decarboxylase. This enzyme converts α -ketoglutarate to succinic semialdehyde, which is then converted to succinic acid by succinate semialdehyde dehydrogenase [51,52]. *M. tuberculosis* can generate energy from many sources, including carbohydrates, lipids, ketones, alcohol, acetone, and hydrocarbons, with over 200 oxidoreductases, oxygenases, and dehydrogenase-transferases [14]. In addition, it has a unique cytochrome P450 that acts as an oxygen transferase to organic groups, which enables the bacteria to synthesize various lipids that are the building blocks of its complex cell envelope [53].

Fig 3: Pathway for the metabolism of glycerol by *M. tuberculosis*. a: glycerol kinase, b: glycerol phosphate dehydrogenase, c: triosephosphate isomerase, d: fructose bisphosphate aldolase. Glyceraldehyde-3-PO₄ enters the glycolytic pathway, while Fructose-1,6-bisphosphate enters the gluconeogenesis pathway (*Sketched with Marvin Sketch 2019*).

M. tuberculosis changes metabolic life as the disease progresses. Due to the need to replicate rapidly, the pathogen accesses host macrophage glucose at the point of macrophage colonization. As the infection progresses, a glucose-oxygen deficient granuloma created by immune cells forces the pathogen to switch to other lipids as carbon sources, resulting in *M. tuberculosis* resorting to anaplerotic carbon fixation (proper only to plants) [16,54]. To accomplish carbon fixation, *M. tuberculosis* evolved four critical enzymes to reverse TCA. Four types of fumarate

reductase (Flavoprotein A, B, C, D) convert fumarate to succinate using ubiquinol as an electron donor [52]. Succinate, an intermediate of this reaction, is pumped out as a cell membrane stabilizer to reduce oxidative stress [52,55]. The point of carbon fixing is the reductive carboxylation of Succinyl CoA to 2-oxoglutarate by a heterodimer oxoglutarate ferredoxin oxidoreductase (OGOR). Isocitrate dehydrogenase converts 2-oxoglutarate to isocitrate by adding a carbon. Then, there is the ATP citrate lyase, which converts citrate to oxaloacetate and acetyl-CoA, which is needed

to continue the carbon fixation process and synthesize cellular molecules. There are speculations that *M. tuberculosis* could even operate reductive TCA by other means, such as reductive carboxylation of pyruvate or phosphoenolpyruvate to malate and oxaloacetate. In extreme conditions, *M. tuberculosis* has also been found to survive on carbon monoxide as a carbon source by synthesizing carbon monoxide dehydrogenase, which converts CO to CO₂, incorporating it into the anaplerotic pathways [35,54].

Lipid metabolism

M. tuberculosis has a high lipid content in its cell envelope, which requires robust biosynthetic machinery for lipid metabolism. Genomic analysis indicates that 8-9% of the *M. tuberculosis* genome codes for multiple copies of genes responsible for lipid biosynthesis, including 36 alleles for *fadD*, encoding acyl-CoA, and 36 alleles for *fadE*, encoding acyl-CoA hydrogenase [56]. These enzymes are crucial in synthesizing acetyl-CoA and the Krebs cycle and glyoxylate pathway [24,57]. The high lipid content (approximately 40% dry mass) of *M. tuberculosis* cells requires the synthesis of lipids using glycerol and acetate as the closest lipid precursors [6,58]. *M. tuberculosis* can break down glycerol in vitro, which leads to the production of molecules that can be used in the glycolytic pathway (Fructose-6-phosphate), TCA (phosphoenol pyruvate), and anaplerotic pathways (oxaloacetate). However, in vivo, the bacterium has two options for utilizing glycerol: it can either break down host lipid (cholesterol) or use glycerol-3-phosphate in host cytosol [55,59].

Cholesterol is abundant on macrophage cell membranes and is a carbon source for phagocytosed *M. tuberculosis*. *M. tuberculosis* captures host cytosol and membrane cholesterol using a transporter controlled by the *mce4* operon [60,61]. Mutants lacking the *Mce4* steroid transporter struggle to persist in

the lungs and are eliminated in IFN γ -activated macrophages [62]. The steroid rings of the cholesterol moiety are the first to be attacked and metabolized into acetyl-CoA (Fig. 4). Then, the aliphatic portion of the cholesterol is assimilated into existing lipids or broken down to acetyl-CoA through beta-oxidation. This breakdown yields Propionyl CoA, Acetyl CoA, and pyruvate, feeding into various pathways, including the glyoxylate shunt, TCA cycle, glycolysis, methyl citrate pathways (catabolism), methylmalonyl, and gluconeogenesis (anabolism) [24,52,55,63]. A Vit B12-dependent methylmalonyl pathways break down Propionyl CoA derived from cholesterol into various lengths of fatty acids, or converts it into succinyl-CoA for entry into the TCA cycle. Propionyl CoA also combines with oxaloacetate to form methyl citrate via the methyl citrate pathway. This compound is broken down into TCA intermediates, succinate, and pyruvate by methyl isocitrate lyase. Therefore, cholesterol can act as a carbon and energy source, providing necessary precursor metabolites for the efficient functioning and replication of the bacilli [24].

Mycobacteria Cell Envelope

The cell envelope of tubercle bacilli is a crucial cellular component that plays a vital role in the cell's survival. Apart from conferring shape to the cell, this covering involves numerous biochemical activities as it interacts with its surroundings [64]. Operating as a selectively permeable barrier, it ensures that only essential substances necessary for survival enter the cell interior [65]. The mycobacterial cell envelope comprises a cell membrane and a core that contains various lipids. This core is known as the mycelial-arabinogalactan-peptidoglycan complex (mAGP), which consists of a peptidoglycan wall parallel to the cell membrane on the inside and covalently linked to a parallel layer of galactofuranose sugars on the outside. The galactofuranose layer is further linked to

highly branched arabinofuranose sugars. Mycolic acids of various configurations are attached perpendicularly to this arabinogalactan layer. In addition to mycolic

acid, many complex lipids are non-covalently bound at multiple positions within the cell envelope, as shown in Fig. 5 [66,67].

Fig 4: Pathways for the metabolism of cholesterol. Propionyl CoA is synthesized from the side chain of cholesterol to succinate in the methyl citrate pathway. From Propionyl through methyl malonyl to succinate is the methyl malonyl pathway. Both pathways lead to gluconeogenesis for the synthesis of carbohydrates. The aliphatic side chain is either assimilated into lipids or broken down into bits by β -oxidation. Gluconeogenesis is initiated by the enzyme Phosphoenolpyruvate carboxykinase (PEPCK), which breaks down oxaloacetate to PEP, which the Glyoxylate shunt enzyme, isocitrate lyase, catalyzes the methyl citrate pathway.

The Peptidoglycan of M tuberculosis

The peptidoglycan of *M. tuberculosis* has the basic architecture of a gram-positive bacterium: two parallel strands of alternating amino sugars, N-acetylglucosamine (GlcNAc), linked by β -1,4 glycosidic bonds to N-acetylmuramic acid (MurNAc), and held together by two perpendicular amino acid

chains [66]. The tetra-amino acid peptide chains are attached to the lactoyl residue of each MurNAc with a specific sequence of l-alanyl- γ -d-isoglutamyl-meso-diaminopimelate-d-alanyl-d-alanine [67,68]. Schleifer and Kandler proposed two main classes of gram-positive bacterial PG, labeled as Groups A and B. For Group A, a crosslink occurs between the *w*-amino group of the

diamino acid in position 3 (Diaminopimelic acid has two amine groups, one is linked to D-glutamic acid, leaving a free amine group-w-for reaction) and the D-alanine in position 4 of the adjacent stand (E.coli, Streptococcus sp., mycobacteria sp., micrococcus sp.). For Group B, crosslink occurs between the α -carboxyl group of glutamic acid in position two and the carboxyl group of D-alanine in position 4 (Microbacterium lacticum, Athrobacter, Corynebacterium insidiosum) [69].

Studies have indicated that the cell wall of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* complex (MTBC) possesses a unique composition that classifies it under Group A1 γ . This group is characterized by the presence of meso-diaminopimelic acid (mDAP) on position 3 of the peptide chain, which crosslinks with D-alanine of the opposite peptide strand, and the D-isoglutamate (D-iGlu) acid and mDAP are amidated. In addition, the free carboxyl group of some of the D-iGlu may be modified by adding the amino acid glycine [65,70]. The resilience of *M. tuberculosis* PG lies in the strength of the peptide crosslinks holding the glycan layers. According to Crick *et al.*,(2008) and Angala *et al.*, (2014), three factors

contribute to the PG strength: (a) the D-D (4-3) amide bond between D-Alanine (D-Ala) and mDAP making up 20-40% of PG, (b) the L-D (3-3) ester bond between mDAP and other mDAP making up 60-80%, and (c) a high percentage (70-80%) of the free moieties within the crosslink available for non-covalent binding of other cell envelope structures [70,71]. However, Angala *et al.* (2014) and Maitra *et al.* (2019) have differing opinions on the effect of an increase in L-D linkage on the growth of the *M. tuberculosis* population. While Maitra *et al.* insist that L-D peptide crosslink accounts for 80% of the total crosslink as the organism approaches the stationary stage and enters the dormant stage, Angala *et al.* believe that the percentage remains constant throughout the growth of the organism [70,71]. Given that the permeability of the cell covering primarily relies on the L-D bond, investigating the impact of changes in L-D linkage as the organism enters dormancy is worth exploring for therapeutic reasons. Is it possible that this bond reinforces impermeability and contributes to sustaining the organism in a dormant state, potentially contributing to patient relapse?

Fig. 5 Schematic description of the MTBC cell envelope.

Another significant variation in the MTBC PG is the glycosylation of the glycan backbone. Past studies show that the muramic acid residues in the PG are all glycosylated. However, a recent study by Bhamidi *et al.* (2011) challenges this notion, suggesting that both forms of muramic acid can be found in a ratio of approximately 1:1 [72,73]. It can be conclusively said that the *Mtb* cell wall glycan backbone is composed of N-acetyl glucosamine (GlcNac) alternating with either N-acetyl muramic acid (MurNac) or N-glycosyl muramic acid (MurNGlyc) [69,72]. The various modifications that strengthen the MTBC peptidoglycan can be the subject of drug research.

Arabinogalactan (AG)

The layer above the peptidoglycan (PG) is a complex structure of heteropolysaccharides composed of arabinose (C5) and galactose (C6) in furanose forms. The AG consists of a linear galactan bed of 23-30 galactose residues that runs parallel to the PG and anchors a tree-like arabinan chain [70]. These galactan residues are held together by glycosidic bonds, which alternate between β 1,5 and β 1,6 bonds [β -D-Galf-(1 \rightarrow 5)- β -D-Galf-(1 \rightarrow 6)]_n [74]. The arabinan tree has two parts: a core and a terminus. The core consists of α -1,5 linked arabinofuranose residues with 3,5- α -D-Araf as branching points. The terminus, composed of 28-30 arabinose residues with eight endpoints containing non-repeating motifs of [β -D-Araf-(1 \rightarrow 2)- α -D-Araf]₂-3,5- α -D-Araf-(1 \rightarrow 5)- α -D-Araf. About 70-80% of the hexa-arabinofuranoside is mycolated. The arabinan heteropolymer binds the galactan backbone with an α -1,5 bond at 1,6 linked galactofuran (Galf).

Within the internally branched 3,5 arabinose residues, galactosamine (GalNH₂) and succinyl substituents are found in a 1:3 ratio per AG molecule. Brennan *et al.* 2003 and

Crick *et al.* (2008) agree that three units of arabinofuranose are attached for every stretch of galactofuranose [72,75]. In contrast, Angala *et al.* (2014) support the view of two arabinofuranose domains per stretch of galactofuranose [70]. Finally, an oligosaccharide interbridge connects the mycolate-arabinogalactan (mAG) to the PG. This diglycoside interbridge comprises a deoxysugar, L-rhamnopyranose (Rhap), and N-acetyl glycosyl-1-phosphate (GluNAcp). The Rhap covalently binds with the first Galf (glycosidic bond) of the galactofuranose bed, while GluNAcp forms a phosphodiester bond with MurNac of the PG. Non-covalently linked lipids are interspersed within the mycolate region [70,76]. These numerous linkages and branchings give the cell envelope its strength and impermeability.

M tuberculosis Cell Envelope Lipids

Lipids are in various forms in living cells, such as fats, phospholipids, steroids, isoprenoids, etc. Within the cell envelope of *M tuberculosis*, lipids are extensively distributed in the cell membrane as a phospholipid bilayer, intercalate within the mAGP and in the outer layer (above the AG), forming a free-flowing hydrophobic meshwork [75]. Mycolic acid and its variants are the most abundant lipids in the Mtb cell envelope. Mycolic acid is a fatty acid with lengthy aliphatic chains bearing various functional groups along its length [77]. The mycolic acids found in Mycobacteria come in diverse lengths, ranging from C60 to C90, and can incorporate substituents, including oxy, methoxy, epoxy, and keto groups (Fig. 6). Bound to the arabinan terminals of the AG layer are three variants of mycolic acid: α -mycolic acid (devoid of oxygenated moieties), cis and trans methoxy mycolic acid, and cis and trans keto mycolic acid [77,78]. 5.3.1.

Free Lipids in Outer Layer

Lipids in the outer layer are diverse and complex in their distribution and molecular constituents. There are four groups of lipids in this layer: acyl-trehalose, sulphated acyl-trehalose, acylated polyketide diol (APD), and acyl-phosphatidyl-myo-inositol mannoside. Acyl-trehaloses have mycolated and non-mycolated variants in mono to multi-acylated forms. Mycolated acyl trehalose glycolipids include trehalose monomycolate (TMM) and trehalose dimycolate (TDM or cord factor), while non-mycolate trehalose includes diacyl trehalose ester (DAT), tri-acyl trehalose ester (TAT), and penta-acyl trehalose ester (PAT). The second carbon of non-mycolated DAT, TAT, and PAT trehalose carries a single straight-chain fatty acid moiety, such as palmitic acid (C16), tuberculostearic or stearic acid (C18). Mycolated acyl trehaloses include methyl-branched fatty acids such as dimethyl-branched mycosanoic acids (C21-25), trimethyl-branched mycolipenic (C25-27), or mycolipanic (C24-28) [56,77,79].

Sulphated trehalose (SL) glycolipids carry a sulphated palmitic or stearic acid at position 2 of the primary glucose moiety. Positions 3, 6', and 6 of the trehalose may have various methylated fatty acids moieties, including hepta or octal methyl-branched phthioceranic and hydroxyphthioceranic acids, resulting in SL variants (36). Found near the bacilli's surface as part of the outer capsule-like layer, acylated diols comprise two families of dimycoserolate esters (DIM). The apolar diol backbone of DIM consists of a 35-carbon chain bearing methyl or methylene groups with two reactive hydroxyl groups esterified. The members of this family of lipids include phthiocerol dimycoserolates (PDIM) and phenolic glycolipids (PGL) [70,80].

The basic unit of members of the Phosphatidyl-myo-inositol-mannosides lipid family is phosphatidylinositol (PI), a 1, phospho-inositol, acylated at the phosphate group with palmitic and tuberculostearic acids.

When mannose moieties are attached to positions 2 and 6, phosphatidyl-inositol-mannoside (PIM) is formed. Notably, the mannose at the 2-position undergoes acylation with a long-chain fatty acid (36). Singh highlights that while *M. tuberculosis* exhibits various degrees of acylation and mannosylation of PIM, the two most prevalent PIMs are tetra acyl PM (Ac₂PIM₂ and Ac₂/PIM₆) [24].

PIM acts as a glycoconjugate and is the precursor for two important glycoconjugates: Lipomannan (LM) and Lipoarabinomannan (LAM). Lipomannan consists of a PIM anchor covalently linked to a lengthy chain of 20-27 mannopyranose residues. These residues are connected by an α -1,6 glycosidic bond, with mono-mannosides held by α -1,2 glycosidic bonds. In contrast, Lipoarabinomannan comprises LM and a tree-like arrangement of D-arabinofuranose, similar to AG [24,76]. In fast-growing Mycobacteria, the non-reducing terminals of LM and LAM at the outer layer are bound by a thick network of polysaccharides (mannose and arabinose in furanose and pyranose forms), and myo-inositols called Manlyated LAM (ManLAM) [81]. Notably, in *M. tuberculosis*, the ManLAM is capped by incorporating an α -(1,4)-linked methyl-thio-D-xylose (MTX) residue [82,83].

The PIM, LM, and LAM are situated on the cell membrane, extending through the PG-AG-mycolic acid layers to the outer layer, while finding them freely floating in the outer layer. During cell division, some of these cell wall components are lost to the environment and have become biomarkers for the detection of TB. Notably, LAM has been explored in the early diagnosis of TB. In 2015, the WHO conditionally approved the use of the lateral-flow TB-LAM assay for TB diagnosis under certain conditions, which is widely used to aid in diagnosing TB [84].

Fig 6: Structure of various fatty acids found on the cell covering of *M. tuberculosis*. Mycolic acids have a hydrophilic head and a hydrophobic tail. The FAS I complex forms the short arm, while the FAS II complex extends a palmitic acid to form the longer arm. (Drawing made with Marvin Sketch, 2019).

Biosynthesis of Cell Envelope

M tuberculosis PG biosynthesis

Peptidoglycan (PG) synthesis in *M tuberculosis* follows a pattern similar to other eubacteria but with some modifications [71].

The process begins when fructose-6-phosphate, a byproduct of the glycolytic pathway, binds to glutamine, forming glucosamine-6-phosphate (GluN-6-P), and through a series of events, UDP-glucosamine

is formed in the presence of uridine diphosphate. Some of the UDP-glucosamines are used to produce UDP-N-acetylmuramoyl-L-alanyl-D-glutamyl-meso-2,6-diaminopimeloyl-D-alanyl-D-alanine called Park's nucleotide [85]. This nucleotide is translocated to an isoprenyl membrane receptor C55 at the inner portion of the cell membrane by a phosphor-N-acetylmuramyl pentapeptide translocase (MraY). Mycobacteria use a peculiar C55 molecule, decaprenyl-phosphate, which differs from undecaprenyl phosphate in other bacteria. With the help of a glycosyltransferase (MurG), GluNac is cleaved from UTP-GluNac (formed by phosphorylation of UDP-glucosamines) and translocated to bind the Park's nucleotide, forming Lipid II. It is at this point that modifications take place. Some MurNac moieties are glycosylated by UDP-MurNac hydroxylase (NamH). Meso-diaminopimelic acid is amidated by amidotransferases. D-isoglutamine is also amidated by MurT and GatD enzymes. Finally, flippases translocate the modified Lipid II to the periplasmic space [71,73].

During the final step of bacterial cell wall synthesis, the newly formed peptidoglycan (PG) must be incorporated into the growing PG. Penicillin-binding proteins (PBPs) play a crucial role in this process. They possess glycosylase and transpeptidase enzymes to link new PG units to existing ones and connect the peptide crosslinks. Class A PBPs catalyze the glycosylation of the N-terminal of MurNac of the Lipid II and the GluNac terminal of the existing PG. This results in the release of Dec-P, which returns to the cytoplasm and becomes available for fresh PG unit synthesis [64,86]. In addition to PBPs, another enzyme called PonA plays a role in crosslinking the penultimate D-alanine and mDAP of opposite peptide chains. This results in the breaking of the D-D dialanyl bond of the new peptide, which releases the terminal D-alanine for crosslinking. In Mycobacteria, the PG is

further strengthened by crosslink formation between mDAP of opposite peptide chains, a process that L, D-transpeptidases catalyze. Except for the carbapenem class, this additional bond is highly resistant to β -Lactam drugs [71].

Synthesis of Arabinogalactan

In the synthesis of AG, each portion is synthesized separately and then transported to bind to existing structures. The Galf section is synthesized when UDP-GluNac is joined to a polyprenyl-P-carrier lipid, decaprenyl phosphate. The resulting Dec-P-P-GluNac complex then binds to a rhamnose residue, completing the link and yielding UDP-Galf that consists of two Galf molecules [70]. The galactosyltransferase enzyme transfers the two Galf molecules from the UDP-Galf-decaprenyl complex to an existing stretch of Galf molecules, called GLFT1&2. This GLFT1&2 is bound to UDP, and the carrier is then translocated to the periplasm, where the nascent Galf binds to existing ones on the PG while the cleaved carrier translocates into the cytoplasm [71,85].

The arabinose portion is synthesized through a series of transformations that begin with D-ribose and are coordinated by the same polyprenyl carrier. The decaprenyl carries synthesized Araf molecules to the periplasm, where they bind to existing Araf (36.38). Although yet to be fully understood, hydrolases and ligases are responsible for cleaving the Dec-P carrier (released and returning into the cytoplasm) from the formed AG. Ligases then link the newly formed AG to PG via an ester bond at the P-GlcNac and the MurNac sections. Recent studies have shown that neither mycosylation of the arabinan terminal nor arabinosylation of the galactan chain is a prerequisite for linking the GlcNac-Rhamose-Galf chain to PG [87,88].

Lipid Biosynthesis

Lipids are composed of fatty acids and glycerol. Glycerol is created within the cytosol from phosphoenol pyruvate (PEP), a byproduct of glycolysis. PEP is transformed into glycerol-3-phosphate through a series of reactions. Then, Glycerol-3-phosphate acyltransferase (GPAT) catalyzes the binding of an acyl-carrier molecule to glycerol-3-phosphate, forming lysophosphatidic acid. With further acylation, phosphatidic acid is formed. Cytochrome 5-diphosphate-diacylglycerol then activates phosphatidic acid, forming CDP-diacylglycerol, which acts as a precursor for the glycerol portion of lipids [24,56,66].

Acetyl CoA, a byproduct of pyruvate in the glycolytic pathway, is the starting metabolite in synthesizing long-chain fatty acids. The regular process is the synthesis of acetyl-CoA pyruvate dehydrogenase complex. However, due to high lipid demand, anaerobic pathways are activated to replenish the Acetyl CoA used [56,59]. Acetyl-CoA is then converted to malonyl-CoA, which binds to another molecule of acetyl-CoA. The CoA of both compounds is cleaved off and replaced with an Acyl carrier protein (ACP). The result is forming a hexanoyl-ACP after a five-stage condensation-decarboxylation, hydration, and de-oxygenation process. This process is repeated until the organism has the required length of fatty acid. However, it is essential to note that this process results only in straight-chain fatty acids with a carbon length of 16 or less without any modifications. In other words, its limit is palmitic acid. Fatty acids longer than palmitic acid are synthesized by extending the palmitic acid carbon chain using other enzyme pathways. Enzymes such as β -hydroxy acyl-ACP dehydrase and 2-trans-enoyl-ACP isomerase catalyze double bonds [78]. Cyclopropanes are catalyzed by cyclopropane mycolic acid synthase 1, which converts the double bond to a cyclopropane

ring by transfer of a methylene group from S-adenosyl-L-methionine [89].

Mycolic acids have two arms: a shorter saturated α -chain (C24-26) and a longer meromycolate chain (C30-60). The more extended arm is synthesized as a meromycolate molecule (C30-C60) built up from palmitic acid, and the modifications are catalyzed by a multifunctional polypeptide FAS I and FAS II that perform condensation, keto-reduction, dehydration, and double bond reduction. The shorter is synthesized as palmitic acid using Acetyl-CoA and malonyl-ACP as a carrier [90,91]. Mycocerosic acid, a moiety of DIM, is synthesized from stearic acid by mycocerosic acid synthase using methyl-malonyl-CoA instead of malonyl-ACP. Phiocerol is synthesized by combining hydrated, methylated, and oxymethylated (and other modifications) fatty acids with a long-chain fatty acid such as palmitic acid, catalyzed by Phiocerol Synthesis Polyketide Synthase complex [86]. Phosphatidylinositol (PI), the foundation of PIM, LM, and LAM, is produced from phosphatidyl-myoinositol. It is one of the by-products of CDP-diacylglycerol branching off in the phospholipid biosynthesis pathway. (33). The CapA enzyme catalyzes the initiation of the mannose cap, while the MtxS and MtxT enzymes synthesize DP-MTX and transfer MTX to the LAM mannose caps [81].

Acyl Trehalose Biosynthesis

There are three pathways for the synthesis of the non-reducing disaccharide trehalose. The first pathway, called OtsA-OtsB, involves the condensation of glucose-6-phosphate and UDP-glucose to make trehalose-6-phosphate, which is then dephosphorylated to release trehalose. The second pathway generates trehalose from glycogen by converting its α -1,4 linkage to a 1,1 linkage and cleaving the disaccharides to release trehalose. The third pathway involves the catalysis of an irreversible isomerization of the α -1,4 linkage

of maltose to a 1,1 linkage in trehalose. Interestingly, all three pathways are present in mycobacteria [79,92].

Trehalose monomycolate (TMM) and Trehalose dimycolate (TDM cord factor) are modifications of trehalose, and their synthesis takes place in the cytosol region of the membrane. Trehalose monomycolate (TMM) and Trehalose dimycolate (TDM cord factor) are synthesized in the cytosol region of the membrane. Mycolic acid synthesized in the cytosol is then transferred to preformed acyl trehalose. TMM is formed when a single mycolic acid residue is at the 6-position of trehalose, while TDM is formed when two residues of mycolic acid are present at positions 6 and 6' of trehalose. TMM synthesized in the cytosol is transported outside the cell by the Resistance Modulation and Division Transporter (RND) [8,77].

The synthesis of diacyl and polyacyl trehalose (DAT, PAT) is associated with a group of enzymes consisting of MmpL10 and FadD21 (a fatty-acyl AMP ligase). These enzymes are synthesized by a cluster of genes that share similarities with RND. The ligase loads activated middle-length chain fatty acids onto the enzyme Pks3/4, then elongated them, producing mycolipenic and mycosanoic acids. The enzyme Chp2 transfers these mycolyl fatty acids onto trehalose. It is important to note that trehalose PAT does not have its biosynthetic pathway but is formed by the sequential transacylation of long-chain fatty acids from DAT [24,92]. An *in vitro* study by Hatzios *et al.* (2009) has also identified a Pap3 protein capable of sequentially transferring two palmitoyl groups to positions 2 and 3 of trehalose-yielding DAT. Once synthesized in the cytoplasm, these modified trehaloses are flipped to the periplasmic side of the membrane [93].

Sulpholipids Biosynthesis

The process of biosynthesis of sulpholipids involves several steps. A sulphate group is initially transferred to the trehalose by an enzyme called sulphotransferase, Stf10. Then, using a CoA carrier, Pap2 adds a palmitoyl or stearoyl chain to position 2' of the trehalose. After that, Pks2, a polyketide synthase, synthesizes pthioceranic acids and hydroxyphthiceranic acids using a fatty acid activated by FadD23, an acyl-AMP-ligase. The newly synthesized fatty acid is then transferred to the 3'-position of the trehalose by PapA1, forming an intermediate molecule SL₁₂₇₈. Finally, an unusual diacylation is catalyzed by Chp1, a cutinase-like membranous protein. Chp1 performs a regioselective transacylation by clipping off two already-made acyl chains from SL₁₂₇₈ and transferring them to SL₁₂₇₈ molecule, forming a complete Sulpholipid SL-1 molecule. Lastly, SL-1 is translocated to the cell surface by Sulpholipid-1 addressing Protein Sap [24,63,70].

***M. tuberculosis* Cell Envelope Components: Roles in Survival and Pathogenesis**

M. tuberculosis adapts to a slow growth rate as a survival mechanism during attachment and establishment. Fast growth would counteract the pathogen's stealth and expose it to the host's defense system and subsequent clearance. Once established, Mtb gains momentum, launching an accelerated attack on the host. As the organism modulates its growth rate, it influences the amount and variety of cell envelope components, influencing the organism's establishment, survival, and pathological impact [94]. During the resting or dormant stage, the peptide linkage of the PG (peptidoglycan) consists mainly of LD crosslinks catalyzed by L-D transpeptidases (LdtMt1 and LdtMt2). These crosslinks show resistance to β -lactams. It also produces β -lactamases, known as BlaC [95], to protect its PG. The transpeptidases of Mtb have some

conformational variations due to gene recombination, which results in lower affinity to transpeptidase β -lactams. Additionally, glycosylation of the N-terminal of MurNac enhances the resilience of the PG by a reduction in sensitivity to β -lactam and lysozyme. There are no indications that the modification influences its virulence [95]. When the organism enters a cell expansion stage, it modifies its PG, breaking down some portion to incorporate nascent PG molecules. The hydrolysis of part of the PG releases products such as muramyl dipeptide and muramyl tripeptides, which induce increased production of β -lactamases to protect the exposed PG under reconstruction [71].

Lipids play a role in the pathogenesis of tuberculosis. Many of these lipids stimulate the immune system, triggering responses that favor the pathogen, such as the induction of pro-inflammatory cytokines that attract young and susceptible immune cells that aggregate to form a granuloma, which provides a haven for the pathogen. Anti-inflammatory cytokines are also induced to reduce the activation status of cell-mediated immunity. Mycolic acids act as immunogens and trigger the production of substances like IFN, myeloperoxidase, and TNF- α while suppressing the production of IL-10 [96,97]. Interleukin-10 is a potent anti-inflammatory cytokine that limits the host immune response, prevents tissue damage, and maintains homeostasis. The result is an increase in immune response leading to tissue damage. This is one of the causes of the scarring of the lungs of cancer patients [98].

The exact virulent effect of sulphated glycolipids SL is not yet fully understood. Still, they are thought to contribute to the pathogen's survival within phagocytic cells by inhibiting phagosome acidification and lysosome fusion, activating neutrophils and macrophages, and inducing cytokine production in monocytes and neutrophils.

They upregulate the immune response, destroying the tissues [4,99].

Lipids such as PM, ManLAM, and TDM have been found to cause phagocyte apoptosis, while PIM, SL, and DAT hinder phagosome maturation. ManLAM and α -glucans on the outer layer bind to complement receptor 3 (CR3) on phagocytes in a non-opsonized manner, providing a faster and more efficient route of phagocyte invasion. Decreased levels of LAM lead to increased susceptibility to β -lactam. Oxygenated mycolates and TDM cause foamy macrophages, which amplify inflammation and lead to excessive immune response and tissue injury. The absence of TDM, or cord factor, in non-pathogenic species suggests its role in disease causation. Cord factor impedes the fusion of lysosomes and phagosomes in phagocytes, and it also elicits the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines like TNF α , IL-1 β , IL-6, and IL-12 [79,100,101]. DIM enhances the uptake of bacilli by phagocytes and prevents the acidification of phagosomes by expelling H⁺ATPase from the phagosome membrane. PDIM helps the bacilli evade the humoral immune response by masking the pattern recognition receptors (PPR) on macrophages. At the same time, PGL stimulates the CCR2 of the host, which further promotes the recruitment of susceptible macrophages [102].

Although extensive study exists on the function of different constituents within cell envelopes, caution must be exercised when assessing their effects as virulence factors. This caution stems from notable functional overlaps and fluctuations in conformation and expression levels throughout various infection stages. Moreover, certain elements may depend on the activation of others. Thus, it is prudent to evaluate the collective influence of these factors as the overarching "virulence factor" instead of solely focusing on individual components.

Targeting the Cell Envelope: A Promising Approach for Tuberculosis Drug Development

The formidable cell envelope of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* has long posed a significant challenge in the battle against tuberculosis. However, it also holds the key to effective treatments by serving as a strategic drug target. Current tuberculosis therapies have been successful in the adoption of a treatment strategy involving the combination of multiple drugs. Most drugs attack the cell envelope directly (meropenem and carbapenem) or indirectly (Isoniazid, Rifampicin), causing the components to dislodge and rendering them susceptible to the host's immune mechanisms [103,104]. This leads to cell lysis, reduced immunomodulation and immunostimulation, and a coordinated immune response.

Isoniazid (INH) is a prodrug activated by the KatG enzyme in *M. tuberculosis* [105]. INH produces numerous free radicals that target cell enzymes, especially enoyl acyl carrier protein reductase (InhA). InhA is responsible for fatty acid modification and lipid synthesis, and a loss of function will lead to a depletion of mycolic acids in the cell covering and a loss of cell envelope integrity [109–111]. Since dormant cells do not replicate, INH is potent only in actively dividing cells [106].

Ethambutol inhibits the enzyme Arabinosyltransferase EmbC, which catalyzes the extension of the AG layer. This action affects the strength and integrity of AG and LAM [76,107,108]. Pyrazinamide is a prodrug that interferes with Fatty acid synthase (FAS-I), an enzyme crucial to synthesizing fatty acids. Cycloserine, a second-line TB drug, is an analogue of the amino acid D-alanine. Its presence interferes with two enzymes, L-alanine racemase, responsible for converting L-alanine to D-alanine, and D-phenylalanine synthetase, which integrates D-alanine into the pentapeptide, both crucial for PG formation.

Cycloserine does this by competitive inhibition, an analog of the enzyme's substrate, resulting in weak PG susceptibility to lysozyme and β -lactam [109,110].

Irrespective of the progress made, resistance to TB drugs remains a challenge. Drug-resistant tuberculosis dates back to the late 1940s, shortly after the introduction of streptomycin [111]. Since then, the bacteria have developed resistance to various degrees. Multi-drug resistant tuberculosis (MDR-TB), which is resistant to at least two of the most potent anti-TB drugs, isoniazid and rifampicin, became a significant concern in the 1980s, as reported by Friedel [112,113]. In the 2000s, a more challenging, extensively drug-resistant tuberculosis (XDR-TB) emerged. XDR-TB is resistant to additional drugs and is considered more difficult [114], which calls for continuous research. While a “silver bullet” for TB is elusive, combined therapy is still a potent treatment, considering that many weak links in the bacteria can be explored, as characterized in this review.

Research into new drugs continues to yield potential candidates (Fig. 7). In 2019, Dupont discovered a drug candidate, piperidinol (PIP1), that inhibits the flippase activity of the MmpL enzyme [100]. MmpL is a trehalose monomycolate flippase that translocates mycolic acid across the cell membrane for incorporation in the cell envelope [115]. In 2020, using a whole-cell screening of large compound libraries, a successful design and synthesis of PIP1-containing drug candidates, SQ109, was found potent against *M. smegmatis* [116]. SQ109 is an ethyl diamine (Sackstetter) with a tripartite function inhibiting MmpL3, diffusing the transmembrane proton gradient necessary for cell wall formation, and enhancing macrophage M1 polarization [117]. Some other MmpL3 inhibitors under development include Indoleamide [118], BM212, a Diphenyl pyrrole [115], BM635, a morpholine

derivative [119], and indole-2-carboxamide derivatives [120].

Maged El Sawy *et al.* (2022) studied two compounds, namely 1,2,3 triazole and 1,2,4 triazole hybrid compounds, which showed the potential to inhibit InhA [121]. In another study, Fawzia and colleagues redesigned 1,2,3-triazole. Through cell-based assays, the modified form demonstrated complete inhibition of InhA at a concentration of 10 μ M [122]. Additionally, the compound gravacridonediol, which is a glycosylated alkaloid found in the plant *Ruta graveolens*, proved to be a better inhibitor of InhA than the known triclosan, according to a study by Kamsri in 2019 [123].

Researchers have made progress in identifying vulnerabilities in the complex mycobacterial cell envelope biosynthesis pathways. However, these targets are located deep within the bacteria's multi-layered defenses. The highly hydrophobic mycolate envelope makes it challenging for drug molecules to reach the cytoplasmic space, where many target enzymes and pathways reside. The structural composition and architecture of the TB cell envelope create obstacles that drugs must overcome to reach their target. The lipid domains, the peptidoglycan-arabinogalactan mesh, and the inner membrane all exhibit some degree of impermeability, making it difficult for drugs to penetrate. In addition, a significant proportion of the pathogen population likely exists in a non-replicating persistent state, rendering many drug targets involved in active growth and cell envelope biosynthesis redundant or transcriptionally suppressed. Furthermore, the pathogen resides within immune cells and complex granuloma structures during infection, creating an

additional physical barrier that drugs need to overcome before encountering the first line of the bacterial cell envelope defences. As a result of these multi-layered impediments, achieving adequate intracellular concentration levels at specific enzyme targets or biosynthetic steps has remained challenging for many existing TB drugs and candidates under research and development (R&D). This often requires unacceptably high systemic doses, increasing the risk of toxicity. Innovative drug delivery strategies and formulations are essential to achieve the full potential of promising cell envelope targets. Pharmacological approaches that improve intracellular bioavailability, enable preferential accumulation at granuloma sites, or facilitate densely packed cell envelope penetration could dramatically enhance therapeutic efficacies at lower doses. Some strategies being explored include encapsulating drugs in nanoparticles [124], leveraging bacterial efflux pump inhibitors as adjuvants [125], and developing lipid-based prodrug conjugates [126], liposomal delivery systems for drugs and vaccines [127], and targeted drug delivery strategies. Achieving optimal drug concentrations at the site of infection while minimizing systemic toxicity requires careful consideration of drug properties and formulation strategies. Therefore, combating TB requires a multidisciplinary approach integrating knowledge from pharmacology, microbiology, immunology, and drug formulation sciences. Furthermore, advances in imaging technologies and biomarker identification can facilitate real-time monitoring of drug distribution and efficacy in infected tissues, allowing for more precise and personalized treatment approaches.

Fig 7: Molecular structure of candidate drugs for treatment of Tuberculosis

Conclusion

Ever since its discovery in 1882, *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* has been a significant focus of extensive global research efforts due to its devastating impact on public health around the world. To address the health challenges posed by tuberculosis, particularly the rise of drug-resistant strains, disrupting the integrity and biosynthesis of this complex cell envelope has emerged as a primary strategy. Despite this pathogen's daunting physiological and genetic complexity, targeting vulnerabilities within the cell envelope machinery has shown considerable promise.

Unlike alternative strategies such as targeting the nucleus, mitochondria, or cell signaling mechanisms, which may require challenging dose levels that increase host toxicity risks, cell envelope inhibitors could potentially achieve antimicrobial effects at lower systemic concentrations by exploiting this pathogen-specific vulnerability. Therefore, gaining a comprehensive understanding of *M. tuberculosis*'s unique characteristics is crucial. This will provide valuable insights to guide the strategic development of more effective interventions against this ancient and formidable disease adversary.

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